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AIDAInnova

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MILESTONE REPORT

HIGH GRANULARITY PROTOTYPE FABRICATION 1

MILESTONE: MS18

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Abstract:

Within WP5 (Development of Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors) Milestone MS18 contains the fabrication of several prototypes.

This milestone has been successfully achieved and is reported.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2022

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

Prototyping of several Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors (DMAPS) using three different CMOS technologies (Tower-Jazz 180 nm, LFoundry 110 nm, Tower-Jazz 65 nm) has been successfully performed leading to 2 large area DMAPS chips with full matrix readout (TJ-Monopix2 and TJ-MALTA2) and several prototyping structures. The fabrication is successfully completed and the prototypes now enter their characterisation phases.

1. INTRODUCTION

Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel Detectors (DMAPS) are critical technologies for the AIDAInnova project. According to most detector experts, they constitute the most interesting new direction of pixel detector development. Therefore, they are an essential approach for pixel detectors at present and in planned accelerator experiments.

Within WP5 the development approach branches into two development targets. One focuses on high granularity devices, targeting small pixel dimensions. The other targets the radiation hardness of devices, especially for applications at hadron colliders such as the LHC. In this Milestone Report, we report on the first prototyping level in the development and production of DMAPS devices in different development approaches:

- (1) TJ-Monopix2 and TJ-MALTA2 DMAPS sensors in 180 nm CMOS technology
- (2) ARCADIA sensor prototypes in 110 nm CMOS technology
- (3) Prototypes for exploration of 65 nm CMOS technology
- (4) Mini-Cactus prototypes in 150 nm CMOS technology

This milestone report concentrates on the achieved prototype1 milestones in these developments.

2. HIGH GRANULARITY DMAPS PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT

The development of Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel sensors has followed so far essentially two generally different design approaches (Fig. 1): (a) large electrode design and (b) small electrode design. While within AIDAInnova (a) is the prime approach for high radiation hardness, (b) targets primarily high granularity, i.e. small pixels, and low-noise and low-power operation, albeit with good radiation tolerance. Development of designs (b) is the theme of this report. The low-noise/low-power benefits and the small pixel size trace back to the tiny charge collection electrode, which yields a small capacitance at the amplifier input. On the downside, charge collection (signal) is more ambitious, particularly under operating conditions that cause radiation damage to the structures, as is the case at the LHC. Therefore, the development focuses on achieving radiation-tolerant full charge collection and large signal-to-noise ratio for high hit-detection efficiency.

Fig. 1 Two approaches for DMAPS: (a) large electrode cell design, (b) small electrode cell design.

2.1. LARGE CMOS PIXEL ARRAYS IN TOWER-JAZZ 180 NM TECHNOLOGY (TJ-MONOPIX2 AND TJ-MALTA2)

The two large area chips TJ-MALTA2 (1x2 cm²) and TJ-Monopix2 (2x2 cm²) are developed in 180 nm technology offered by Tower-Jazz and have common front-ends (charge collecting structures) [1]. Both chips are fabricated on a common reticule. The difference rests in the pixel readout architecture: while TJ-Monopix1/2 employs an established column-drain-type readout architecture, TJ-MALTA1/2 features a challenging low-power asynchronous readout needing GHz synchronization. The otherwise very successful production of the Monopix1/MALTA1 prototypes showed an efficiency drop in pixel corners after irradiation which was intensively studied by interim prototyping (miniMALTA) to cure this problem.

The milestones were finally reached with the submission and fabrication of the TJ-Monopix2/MALTA2 chips (Fig. 2). Both designs feature enhanced charge collection and radiation tolerance achieved by applying several measures, including improved implant geometry, higher resistivity wafers and improved analogue amplification electronics, to increase signal and lower the noise. Note that both chips are very large area realisations featuring 512 x 512 pixels with size 33 x 33 μm² (TJ-Monopix2) and 512 x 256 pixels with size 36 x 36 μm² (TJ-MALTA2), respectively. Both are functioning. Characterisation is ongoing and will be reported in future reports.

Fig. 2: Photographs of successfully produced TJ-MALTA2 (left) and TJ-Monopix2 (right). Milestone reached.

2.2. PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT IN LFOUNDRY 110 NM TECHNOLOGY (ARCADIA)

The ARCADIA (Advanced Readout CMOS Architectures with Depleted Integrated sensor Arrays) project aims to develop small electrode devices targeting high granularity and low power dissipation on thin substrates [2]. ARCADIA uses backside bias to improve the charge collection efficiency and timing performance. A series of fabrication runs of these chips are foreseen. The first demonstrator, called ARCADIA-MD1 was fabricated in an engineer run. The devices feature a 512 x 512 matrix of pixel with size 25 x 25 μm^2 which are read out in a triggerless binary mode with an event rate up to 100 MHz/cm². Hardware for the evaluation of the MD1 chips has been developed and the first devices are being electrically evaluated. The characterization is ongoing.

Fig. 3: Photograph of successfully produced ARCADIA-MD1 mounted on a readout board. Milestone reached.

2.3. PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT IN TOWER-JAZZ 65 NM TECHNOLOGY (TJ65)

Future high energy physics experiments will require silicon devices with increased granularity and radiation hardness. DMAPS fabricated on technologies with smaller feature sizes are a natural path to meet these goals. The exploration of these technologies is an important goal of this work package. After discussions with the TowerJazz foundry, TJ 65 nm has been chosen to evaluate the first prototypes. A first multi-layer reticle was fabricated that includes a variety of devices, from transistor prototypes to digital pixel test structures [3].

Fig. 4: Photograph of a quarter of a wafer with test structures produced on the TJ 65 nm technology (left). A detail of the reticle and the structures is shown on the right. Milestone reached.

2.4. PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT IN LFOUNDRY 150 NM TECHNOLOGY (MINI-CACTUS)

DMAPS exploiting both tracking and timing domains are an interesting option for future experiments. Within this work package, an early prototype in the LFoundry 150 nm process called Mini-Cactus has been fabricated to explore this possibility. It features different matrices with various pixel sizes (1 mm to 50 μm), low power consumption and fast peaking times [4]. Ultimately this effort targets a time resolution below 100 ps.

Fig. 5: Photograph of the Mini-Cactus chip mounted on a board for testing. Milestone reached.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The planning envisaged for the DMAPS high granularity approach employing different CMOS technologies and different architectures was executed as initially planned leading to:

- A large prototype matrix TJ-Monopix2 with full readout architecture (column-drain)
- A large prototype matrix TJ-MALTA2 with full readout architecture (asynchronous)
- A first full size demonstrator ARCADIA-MD1 featuring small pixels, binary readout and backside biasing
- The first test structures and small pixel matrices in TJ 65 nm
- A prototype to explore high granularity and excellent time resolution

The devices have been made available to the groups participating in the work package, and their performance is being evaluated. We conclude that with these successful chip submissions, milestone M18 was fully met and can be considered to be accomplished.

4. REFERENCES

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- [3] S. Bugiel et al., “Charge sensing properties of monolithic CMOS pixel sensors fabricated in a 65 nm technology”, 2022 Vienna Conference on Instrumentation. Event online <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1044975/contributions/4663696/>.
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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
DMAPS	Depleted Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors